

OpenStreetMap in the Training of Local Actors in Projects Aimed at Community-Based Interventions in Slums: A Systematic Review Supported by AI

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Keywords: VGI, public participation, community mapping, collaborative mapping, slums.

Abstract

This text aims to analyze the process of training residents from peripheral communities in the use of free geospatial tools, with a special emphasis on OpenStreetMap (OSM). The analysis is based on a literature review, conducted with the aid of generative artificial intelligence tools, seeking to understand the impact of these initiatives in favelas. The primary focus is to explore how the use of OSM, as the world's largest collaborative mapping tool, is utilized for community mobilization, promoting digital inclusion and geospatial knowledge acquisition. Additionally, it highlights the main challenges faced by these initiatives, including an analysis of studies conducted in communities and the continuous engagement of participants. The text also seeks to identify gaps observed in the reviewed literature, pointing out future directions for research and interventions that can further enhance the social and transformative impact of these collaborative mapping tools in favelas.

1. Introduction

Public participation is of utmost importance for the mobilization and engagement of vulnerable communities. Through their networks and relationships, both inside and outside the community, they produce space through social action. The advancement of technologies enabling the generation of volunteered geographic information (VGI) by end users responds to the need for generating data that helps vulnerable communities strengthen ties with public agencies responsible for key interventions that drive change. It is possible to leverage the sensitivity and ability to communicate individual needs, allowing each resident, based on their perception, to understand the needs of their community. Thus, it is crucial to use open and free mapping tools that represent community demands, producing information that allows for collective autonomy in developing strategies involving public authorities through cooperation and coalitions aimed at community-based interventions (Silva, 2014).

In this context, OpenStreetMap (OSM) stands out as an essential collaborative mapping tool for community interventions in highly vulnerable urban areas, such as favelas. Due to the participatory and open nature of OSM, it enables the creation of maps recording various types of features, while also serving as a valuable platform for community training and the development of geospatial skills (Bortolini et al., 2019). This paper aims to deepen the discussion and analyze the literature on how OpenStreetMap has been used for the training and capacity- building of local actors in projects focused on community-based interventions in favelas.

As such, the emphasis on community mapping is placed on generating information that drives actions promoting change within the community, based on the data gathered and discussed. The mapped information is crucial for mediating with public authorities responsible for coordinating urban effectively participate in these processes. More importantly, this training is necessary for these communities to gain autonomy in using and producing information about their territories, thus adopting not only a reactive stance to institutional demands but also a proactive approach in advocating for improvements. planning with community

participation and input. These vulnerable communities often lack technical knowledge and require additional instruction on cartographic elements to

2. Review

2.1 Openstreetmap

The growth of various collaborative mapping tools around the globe has been a reality since the early 21st century. Collaborative mapping processes have diversified to accommodate different methodologies and needs. For these mapping efforts to be carried out, they require a base map, and OpenStreetMap (OSM) has not only established itself as the largest collaborative map in the world but also as an excellent base map for various projects.

Over the past 14 years, numerous projects have deepened the use of OSM as a foundation for humanitarian actions that contribute to the base map. Among these are initiatives such as HOT, Missing Maps, and YouthMappers, along with tools like the HOT Tasking Manager, which manages mapping tasks, and other platforms for sharing global data, such as the Humanitarian Data Exchange. These efforts reflect the growth of humanitarian mapping initiatives and the widespread use of open data, providing an alternative for collaborative data and tools in slums (Helfort et al., 2021).

The ability of open mapping tools to support the generation of information in vulnerable communities is essential for creating base maps, which are fundamental to spatial understanding by the population. The absence of official information, along with access difficulties—whether due to lack of disclosure or the need for devices to view and manipulate data—poses challenges. Moreover, knowledge is crucial for identifying which information is relevant to the community. There is an urgent need for initiatives that bridge the gap between the community and the tools that can assist in local development.

2.2 Community Training in Slums

The variety of mapping tools broadens access for a larger number of users, each with different interests in using these platforms. In vulnerable communities, the use of these platforms aims to promote local development, making it

essential for mapping tools to meet these specific demands. Beyond usage, it is important to understand how the training of individuals can contribute to effective platform use and generate autonomy in the process of producing volunteered geographic information (VGI).

Self-mapping offers autonomy in the process, but for the appropriation and use of these mapping tools to have a real impact on residents' lives, proper instruction is essential. The lack of awareness about the importance of community mapping is a prevalent issue, as vulnerable communities often suffer from a lack of access to essential rights. This underscores the need to assert territory as part of the fight for these rights to achieve social transformation (Bugs et al., 2011).

Coli (2012) emphasizes that the training and use of these mapping tools by the community, aligned with their own goals, have a significant impact on counteracting domination by power groups. Training community leaders in these tools is therefore fundamental, as it gives communities the necessary expertise to promote meaningful changes in their territories.

Popular knowledge has the potential to drive interventions in the community using collaborative mapping resources. However, certain nuances of the mapping process require guidance to ensure the viable and effective use of these tools in gathering community information. To this end, it is crucial to assess both national and international mapping projects and initiatives to observe how the use of OpenStreetMap and platforms that rely on it as a base influence community-based interventions.

2.3 Community-Based Intervention

Building projects in vulnerable communities requires ongoing dialogue between those promoting the initiative and the residents, who have firsthand knowledge of the area. For the project to progress and foster community engagement, it is vital to understand the community's needs, which the group can support. Moreover, it is essential to recognize that exchanging knowledge and perceptions from each resident is fundamental to fostering relationships with the team that seeks to implement actions for local development and social transformation through dialogue.

Community-based intervention, as a concept in local development processes, aims to promote well-being, health, and the reduction of inequalities through community autonomy. To promote these actions, associations, collectives, and engaged groups must define objectives focused on promoting equality, access to quality infrastructure, health promotion, and engagement capacity (McLeroy, 2003). Consequently, community-based intervention strengthens actions that improve public policies through partnerships and participation in the planning of initiatives that impact the community.

3. Methodology

The process of searching for literature on projects, initiatives, and actions focused on training in collaborative mapping requires careful analysis. To understand this process, it is essential to gather a broad range of information to identify similarities and potentials in each action. To enhance the literature review, it is important to use different tools that help diversify the articles found during the search.

In this regard, a systematic literature review was conducted with the support of generative artificial intelligence tools

(ChatGPT-4, Elicit, Semantic Scholar), bibliography management software (Zotero), combined with other research methodologies (P.I.C.O., Bardin) to assist in evaluating the content available in the literature. Although AI tools provide great assistance for the review, they do not replace the need for critical judgment and human expertise, requiring solid knowledge of the content and scientific methodology.

The literature review was carried out in three stages, with each stage expanding the number of search databases and refining the diversity of keywords.

In the first search, the following keywords were used on the WoS and Scopus platforms: [Collaborative mapping, Community intervention, OpenStreetMap, Community empowerment, Community mobilization, Citizen participation]. These keywords were chosen after an analysis of the main research themes, conducted with the support of ChatGPT-4. Filters applied included publication date within the last 10 years and free access to the articles. As a result, 43 articles matching these criteria were found, most of which were in English.

This initial search revealed the need to increase the number of articles specifically addressing the use of OpenStreetMap in favelas and/or informal settlements.

In the second search, the research scope was broadened by including platforms such as Google Scholar. Additionally, the keywords were refined based on the reading of articles found in the first search, especially those most aligned with the topic of interest. Using the refined keywords, they were input into ChatGPT-4 to generate search strings using the P.I.C.O. acronym (Population; Intervention; Comparison; Outcome) for use in Web of Science.

The search string defined for Web of Science was: [{"Collaborative mapping" OR "participatory mapping") AND ("community intervention" OR "community-based intervention") AND ("OpenStreetMap" OR OSM) AND ("community empowerment" OR "empowerment") AND ("community mobilization" OR "community engagement") AND ("citizen participation" OR "public participation") AND (favelas OR "informal settlements" OR "urban slums")].

These same keywords were used in searches on Google Scholar and Scopus, adjusting them for the specific syntax of each search engine. In this stage, fourteen articles were identified in the Web of Science, Google Scholar, and Scopus databases, three of which had already been found in the first stage.

In the third stage, AI tools Elicit and Semantic Scholar were used to find new articles, employing the most frequent keywords from the 57 articles found in stages 1 and 2.

In the fourth stage, a duplicate exclusion analysis was conducted across the three searches, along with the elimination of articles that did not utilize OpenStreetMap or did not directly address the topic. This final analysis was performed ensure that the synthesis framework included only articles with relevant applications or reviews on the subject.

As a result, a synthesis framework1 (Figure 1) was developed with 27 articles, aiming to systematize the information from the identified works by providing: 1. Country of the mapped community, 2. Problem/Objective/Hypothesis, 3. Methodology, 4. Material used, 5. Techniques applied, 6. Key results, 7. Involvement with favelas, 8. Nature of community-based intervention, 9. Whether favela residents operated OpenStreetMap, 10. Location of the favela and/or intervention, 11. For favela mapping, which features and attributes were mapped, 12. Were integrated digital and analog cartographic

technologies used? Which ones? 13. Were methods for the appropriation of cartographic tools and data by the community applied? 14. Did the project provide educational materials? Indicate the link, 15) Was a method used to evaluate the tools and processes employed? 16) Were community impact indicators utilized? 17) Are effective impacts experienced by the community reported? What were they?

Additionally, a fifth stage focused on analyzing articles centered on slum areas. Fourteen questions were crafted, and answers were generated using the AI tool ChatGPT-4 based on 10 articles uploaded into it. Subsequently, each response was analyzed and verified for accuracy against the content presented in the articles. The questions were:

1. Explore the methodologies used in the studies to assess how researchers approach training in collaborative mapping and the use of OpenStreetMap.
- 2.Regarding the relevance of objectives: Examine the objectives of the studies and identify similarities and differences among them.
- 3.Can you also include the identification of gaps in the existing literature or confirmation of current trends?
- 4.Discuss how OpenStreetMap was used in the various studies, including its effectiveness as a community intervention tool.
- 5.Include the discussion from the articles on the accessibility, usability, and ability of OpenStreetMap to meet the needs of favela communities.
- 6.Based on the articles, discuss the gaps and challenges encountered in studies related to mapping training in favelas.
7. From this question, propose methodologies or improvements in the training of OpenStreetMap and other collaborative mapping tools.
8. Discuss the gaps identified in the literature, such as the lack of longitudinal studies or the need for more research in specific regions or social contexts.
9. Conduct a critical analysis of the studies, assessing the robustness of the evidence presented and suggesting areas for future research.
10. Conclude with a discussion of the practical implications of the results, such as the applicability of the tools and methodologies for future community intervention projects.

Figure 1. Synthesis Framework

Thus, in the synthesis framework, it was possible to establish an overview of OpenStreetMap use in favelas, as well as identify the different perspectives observed in the various applications of the tool.

4. Results and Discussion

The analysis of the literature was based on 27 articles listed in the synthesis framework, aiming to understand the main impacts on the OpenStreetMap community, the most commonly used methodologies, research gaps, the spatial dynamics of these actions, and their repercussions on the communities involved.

4.1 Studies overview

It is important to highlight that, in most cases, the literature focuses on reporting and explaining actions carried out in communities. Seven articles delve into literature reviews. Four of them addressed the uses of OpenStreetMap, either for its integration with official data (Camboim, 2021) or for humanitarian mapping (Herfort, 2021; González, et al., 2022; Solís, et al., 2023). Other articles focused on reviews centered on the sustainable development of nations, based on concepts such as "Neocartography" (Choplin et al., 2019) and "Volunteered Geographic Information" (VGI) (Bertolotto et al., 2020), as well as actions at the urban level, such as "urban planning" and "urban management" (Camboim, 2019). Considering the remaining articles (19) (Choplin et al., 2019; Camboim, 2021; Fernandes et al., 2017; Gonzalez et al., 2022; Hennig, 2017; Husen et al., 2018; Junior et al., 2016; Kuffer, et al., 2024; Le Guilcher et al., 2022; Liu, et al., 2018; Mooney et al., 2014; Naim et al., 2021; Pánek et al., 2011; Pánek et al., 2019; Ravisconi, S. et al., 2022; Rivera- Flórez, et al., 2024; Virgens, et al., 2024; Yeboah, et al., 2021; Zacharopoulou et al., 2021), the study areas are predominantly focused on the Global South (Figure 2), with some occurrences in Europe, where studies are aimed at the protection of forest areas and the Sustainable Development Goals.

Figure 2. Distribution of study areas

Among these, ten articles addressed slum areas (10). (Choplin et al., 2019; Fernandes et al., 2017; Kuffer, et al., 2024; Liu, et al., 2018; Pánek et al., 2011; Pánek et al., 2019; Ravisconi, S. et al., 2022; Rivera-Flórez, et al., 2024; Virgens, et al., 2024; Yeboah, et al., 2021.) The case studies are exclusively distributed in the Global South (Figure 3), primarily in Africa and South America. The themes explored include mapping perceived risk for disaster risk management of housing, improving living conditions, and community-based mapping initiatives.

Figure 3. Distribution of study areas in slums

4.2 Mapping tools

It is important to highlight that, as OSM is a platform with basic cartographic information, other open geospatial tools that utilize OSM data are present in the literature found in this review, including: QGIS, OSMTracker, OpenDataKit (ODK), OpenMapKit (OMK), Mapillary, and TeachOSM (Figure 4).

Figure 4. Diagram of tools used In the literature

In the literature, the combined use of these tools is mainly applied to slum mapping, with the objective of generating the first spatial data on these communities. The gathered information includes street-level images and basic mapping of elements such as buildings, sanitation, health, education, and roads. The portion of the articles that did not directly address tool usage focused on thematic reviews of OpenStreetMap, without using the tool itself, limiting their scope to data analysis or thematic discussions. (Machado et al., 2019; Camboim, 2021; Schröder- Bergen et al., 2021; Naim et al., 2023; Pánek et al., 2019; Junior et al., 2016; Pánek et al., 2011)

Regarding mapping tools, it is important to highlight that each community uses different methodologies based on their dynamics of geospatial data collection and analysis. For example, data collected from slum areas in Cotonou, Benin (Choplin et al., 2019), and El Pacifico, Colombia (Rivera-Flórez, et al., 2024). Both studies considered risk areas in self-built communities and used OpenStreetMap to generate basic cartographic information. However, in Benin, OSMTracker and JOSM were used to generate data due to the difficulty in acquiring equipment and environmental conditions. In Colombia, another study focused on a community where the mapping of these data was conducted online, supported by live streaming, online meetings, and mapathons using OpenStreetMap iD.

Although all the articles deal with slums, it is important to emphasize that, while each territory may be similar, there are differences in structure and processes. In this sense, the mapping methods present diverse approaches in the slum study literature, varying in both the tools used and the objectives.

To support this training process, it is important to create training modules and more intuitive platforms that cater to specific needs. This contribution has been made by the Data4HumanRights project (Kuffer, et al., 2024), which developed guides for training

in tools for community interventions. The QuebradaMaps project follows the same approach to territorial training and, as mentioned earlier, also has a methodological guide to contribute to slum training. The reported experiences range from critical territorial training (Fernandes et al., 2017), which seeks to question and reinterpret the community's space, to initiatives aimed at ensuring the presence of these communities on maps, thus contributing to their visibility and existence in the geographical and political landscape (Choplin et al., 2019).

Community-Based Interventions in mapping projects

A synthesis framework was also sought to assess the presence of interventions among community applications. The articles address these actions based on concepts such as "Intervention," "Community Intervention," or "Slum Upgrade." Only a small portion of the articles (5) reported the occurrence of interventions in the studied communities

(Choplin, et al., 2019; Liu, et al., 2018; Pánek et al., 2019; Rivera-Flórez, et al., 2024; Virgens, et al., 2024). It is important to note that these interventions had diverse approaches. Some included the creation of mapping panels for the communities, allowing the population, armed with this information, to advocate for improvements with public authorities. Other projects, such as MapKibera (Panek et al., 2019), focused on creating community data and improving local conditions. This type of action was also observed in Brazilian communities, such as Salvador and Niterói (Virgens et al., 2024). The use of OpenStreetMap as a tool for community intervention was predominant in most projects, being used to generate basic information, as in the case of a study in Bogotá, Colombia, where the base data was used to map vulnerable areas. Similarly, actions were carried out in marginalized and neglected communities by public authorities in Cotonou, Benin (Choplin, et al., 2019).

It is necessary to identify in the articles the type of intervention and what improvements were made and perceived by the population. According to McLeroy, it is essential to recognize intervention from the perspective of promoting equality, access to quality infrastructure, health promotion, and capacity building. In this sense, these actions must also be present in slum project methodologies.

4.3 Identified Gaps in the Studies

The vast range of OpenStreetMap applications identified in the articles allows for collaborative actions to be carried out in conjunction with community projects. However, it is still possible to identify a lack of specific training in these tools, which limits their use, especially among individuals with low digital literacy. The lack of digital literacy among slum users also reflects the difficulty in achieving sustainable development goals (Reddy et al., 2020), reflecting the context of poverty, inequality, and education.

Among the various actions carried out in communities discussed in the articles, one similarity stands out: the absence of an in- depth discussion on the continuity and sustainability of interventions. Although the actions focus on the application of methodologies, the articles do not emphasize longitudinal studies in these territories.

5. Conclusions

The analysis of the approaches adopted by projects in terms of training and education, including the provision of educational materials and methods for the appropriation of cartographic tools and data, reveals important strategies for empowering local communities. We are still investigating the characteristics and attributes mapped specifically in favelas, with the aim of identifying the main challenges and needs of these areas. This analysis will provide valuable insights for improving the methodologies and mapping tools used in these urban contexts.

The importance of appropriate training that meets community needs and provides ongoing support strengthens these actions within the community. The synthesis framework presented reflects a comprehensive overview of the current state of OpenStreetMap use for training and intervention in favelas, identifying gaps, challenges, and opportunities. The focus is on maintaining the pursuit of innovations and the constant updating of information, with the goal of contributing to the enhancement of future research and projects aimed at strengthening and transforming social conditions in communities.

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